

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.18 Report from the second webinar

Public

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1. Summary

This document is a part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Work Package (WP6). The goal of the deliverable D6.18 “Report from the second webinar” is to report on the 2nd CYCLOPES webinar, which was held online on 7th December 2023. This webinar is a part of task 6.4. and provides an additional option to engage stakeholders within the Cybercrime community.

These webinar sessions are running annually and are organised in cooperation with partner networks established through WP5, in an effort to maximise impact and to amplify participation. The subject of 2nd webinar ‘**Enterprises as a Victims of Cybercrime**’ has been chosen in collaboration with **European Judicial Cybercrime Network (EJCN)**.

2. Introduction

The project dissemination activities in general and the webinars in particular, are mainly construed as CYCLOPES Community networking events and focus on sharing the results among the identified and newly identified community members, stakeholders and other relevant audience of interest.

The webinars are used to complement the activities of WP2 and WP3; since the CYCLOPES workshops and Joint Live Exercises are for practitioners only, the annual webinars are ideal to reach out to a wider audience. They are used to conclude previous discussions or to launch new topic areas to be explored further. For the first webinar, the topic ‘Social Engineering aspect of Cybercrimes affecting People’ was chosen to build on the results of the 3rd CYCLOPES workshop on this topic.

The CYCLOPES Community members and stakeholders’ audience are the core of the main goals of the CYCLOPES communication and dissemination activities. Throughout the duration of the project, CYCLOPES intends to build and sustain efficient community members relations in order to enable interaction between different parties and build synergies with already established networks of practitioners. Therefore, it was decided that the 2nd webinar will be organised in cooperation with European Judicial Cybercrime Network (EJCN) and will cover the various legal and practical aspects of remediation for victims and similar cases of cybercrime. This time, the webinar was dedicated only for CYCLOPES Consortium, Law Enforcement Agencies, prosecutors, and judicial experts from the EJCN, specialised in countering the challenges of cybercrime and cyber-enabled crime. CYCLOPES project also connects and builds synergies between Member State LEAs and industry and academia partners by stimulating and sustaining dialogue on pressing European Cyber security matters. We realise that it would be valuable to focus on companies and protection of their rights as a victims of crime in national prosecution procedures and operational challenges in this area.

3. 2nd CYCLOPES Webinar

3.1. Main goal and program of the webinar

‘Cybercrime’ is an umbrella term that refers to all criminal activities that are carried out over the internet. There are various different cybercrime activities performed every day, and the list continues to grow as cybercriminals adopt new technologies and methods. While cybercrime used to be a concern only for larger enterprises with a significant online presence, that is no longer the case in recent years. In fact, many cybercriminals are now targeting smaller businesses and organizations since they know that small businesses tend to have weaker security infrastructure.

Therefore, CYCLOPES in cooperation with EJCNC decided to hold a webinar on 7th December 2023, focusing on following points:

- the importance of reporting attacks and cyber-enabled crimes by companies
- the implications of a cyberattack for companies and the tools available to reduce vulnerability
- the ways to secure evidence
- the relevant legal steps that can help the victim of cybercrime seek redress

The goal of the webinar was also to foster networking activities and raise awareness of the EJCNC and CYCLOPES. The agenda of the webinar is presented here:

The slide features the CYCLOPES logo at the top left and the title 'AGENDA OF THE 2nd WEBINAR' in large teal letters. On the left, there are two circular images showing a webinar session. The agenda items are listed in a table format on the right side of the slide. At the bottom left, there is a European Union flag and a small text box providing funding information.

Time	Topic	Speaker
12:00 - 12:05	WELCOME AND INTRODUCTION TO THE WEBINAR	Claudia Pinia, European Judicial Cybercrime Network (EJCNC) Rashel Talukder, Polish Platform for Homeland Security, CYCLOPES Project Coordinator
12:05 - 12:35	RANSOMWARE - THE SCOURGE OF BUSINESS	Paul Johnstone, Garda National Cyber Crime Bureau
12:35 - 13:05	LEA'S PERSPECTIVE	Eli Hoyberghs, Belgium Federal Police
13:05 - 13:35	WHY ARE THE VICTIMS IMPORTANT?	Knut Jostein Sætnan, NCIS Norway
13:35 - 13:40	CLOSING REMARKS	

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Figure 1 Agenda of the 2nd webinar

3.2. Results of the webinar

The event had 147 registered participants: LEAs, prosecutors and judicial experts across Europe and CYCLOPES Consortium members. The final audience of attending participants was 75.

The following key points from the presentations and discussion have been identified:

1. Ransomware has emerged as a major threat to businesses.
2. Ransomware is distributed in a variety of ways and is difficult to protect against because it is constantly evolving and every person and business with internet access is vulnerable.
3. According to the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), if the ransomware attacks/incidents involve personal information, then it must be reported.
4. Many countries are creating their own privacy law model based on the GDPR regulations. For example, in the Netherlands its mandatory by law for the victim companies to report the incidents (ransomware) to the authorities.
5. The importance of reporting an attack on a company is important to counter them effectively.
6. There should be more cooperation between LEAs and judicial authorities and:
 - a. companies providing cybersecurity tools and solutions

- b. internet service providers
 - c. cybersecurity centers
 - d. law-makers
7. Different data retention policies across Europe is a challenge.
 8. Norway has good experiences with establishing cooperation with business to prevent and fight cybercrime through Private Sectors Liaison Officers
 9. It would be interesting to organise an international hackathon for LEAs, prosecutors and judges to work on international cybercrime cases.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable summarises the 2nd CYCLOPES webinar, which provided an additional opportunity to engage stakeholders within the fighting cybercrime community. During the productive discussion, participants were able to share their thoughts and opinions in relevant matters related to the topic of the webinar 'Enterprises as a victims of cybercrime'. The 3rd CYCLOPES Webinar is planned for the first half of 2024.